

Guishen zhi ming 鬼神之明

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Entry tags: Divine powers, Early Chinese Traditions, Religious Group, Early Chinese text, Text, Language, Sino-Tibetan, Chinese Religion, Excavated text, Confucianism, Sichuan and Hanzhong Valley Region

Guishen zhi ming 鬼神之明 (The Brilliant Insight of Ghosts and Spirits) is the title given to a bamboo manuscript included in the Shanghai Museum collection. It is a looted bamboo manuscript acquired by the Shanghai Museum from the Hong Kong Antiquities Market in 1994. The manuscript has been dated by archaeologists around 300 BCE and it is deemed to be an original product from the southern state of Chu 楚. Ding Sixin 丁四新 proposed the alternative title Guishen 鬼神 (Ghosts and Spirits) for this manuscript, based on the tradition of juxtaposing two main words from the first sentence. It is a short text inked on five bamboo strips (the fifth being shared with the Rongshi you chengshi 融師有成氏) that includes a total of 197 characters (211 when counting the recovered ones, according to Cao Jinyan 曹锦炎). The transcription of the text is found in Ma Chengyuan 马承源, Shanghai Bowuguan Zhanguo Chu zhushu 上海博物館戰國楚竹書 vol. 5. Similarly to the Mozi 墨子 (with particular reference to the Ming Gui 明鬼 III section, since sections I and II are now lost), the Guishen zhi ming argues for the existence of ghosts and spirits, strengthening the prominence of this theme within the Warring States (475–221 BCE) religious and philosophical discourse. But contrary to the Mozi and to Confucian view, this text states that in some realms ghosts and spirits are indeed perspicuous, while in others they are not. Just as in the Mozi, however, ghosts and spirits cover the role of rewarders and punishers of humans, based on people's behavior – although, according to the author of this manuscript, ghosts and spirits are not omniscient. The existence of ghosts and spirits is not questioned; what the author is skeptical about is the ability of these beings to recognize people's individual instances of merit and guilt so that they can be rewarded or punished accordingly. This limiting view of the abilities of ghosts and spirits, absent from the debate that emerges from the transmitted tradition, offered additional nuance to the religious discussion of the Warring States period. The manuscript, in line with Mozi's view and sharing the same vocabulary, refers to instances in which indeed ghosts and spirits reward the good and punish the wicked (賞善罰暴), bringing the example of the virtuous sovereigns of antiquity Yao 堯, Shun 舜, Yu 禹, and Tang 湯 and of the tyrants Jie 桀, Zhou 紂, You 幽, and Li 厲. But the manuscript also brings contrary examples: those cases in which a wise ruler is not rewarded (the case of Wu Zixu 伍子胥) or a wicked one is not punished (Duke Yi of Rong 榮夷公). By using *huo* 或 (sometimes) the manuscript clarifies the underlying idea that justice at the hands of ghosts and spirits is not inevitable, but rather sporadic: 如以此詰之，則善者或不賞，而暴者或不罰。The text also proposes possible reasons behind this lack of *ming* 明 (brilliant insight, perspicuity) on the side of the ghosts and spirits, posing two possible scenarios, but avoiding making a choice among the two: one possibility is that ghosts and spirits actually have the strength and the capacity (*neng li* 能力) to always be perspicuous, yet they choose to not do so; the second possibility is that they wish to possess a firmer strength (*li* 力), but they do not.

Date Range: 400 BCE - 300 BCE

Region: Chu State

Region tags: Asia, East Asia

The southern state of Chu 楚 around the 4th century BCE (Warring States China)

Status of Readership:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Ma Chengyuan 马承源, ed., Shanghai Bowuguan Zhanguo Chu zhushu 上海博物館藏戰國楚竹書, vol. 5 (Shanghai: Shanghai guji chubanshe, 2005), 307–320.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://projects.zo.uni-heidelberg.de/manuscript/index.php/manuscripts/show/368>
- Source 1 Description: Manuscripts Database of the Institute of Chinese Studies of the University of Heidelberg

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Written

Inked

- with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Bamboo

Notes: The text is written on 5 bamboo slips (for a total of 197 graphs), acquired by the Shanghai Museum from the Hong Kong Antiquities Market in 1994, together with a total of circa 1200 bamboo slips, dated around 300 BCE. Ding Sixin 丁四新 proposed as an alternative title "Guishen 鬼神" (Ghosts and Spirits).

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

- Other [specify]: Field doesn't know.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

- Other [specify]: Field doesn't know.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb

– Yes

Notes: The Guishen zhi ming 鬼神之神 is a looted manuscript, presumably robbed from a Chu 楚 tomb, but we have no precise information about its provenance.

↳ Cemetery

– Field doesn't know

Notes: If the manuscript was indeed excavated from a tomb, that tomb possibly was part of a cemetery area, but unfortunately, we have no precise information about that.

↳ Temple

– No

↳ Shrine

– No

↳ Altar

– No

↳ Devotional marker

– No

↳ Cenotaph

– No

↳ Church

– No

↳ Mosque

– No

↳ Synagogue

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

↳ Library/archive

– No

↳ Specify

– Specify: The manuscript has been looted, most probably from a tomb, and is now stored at the Shanghai Museum that acquired it from the Hong Kong Antiquities Market in 1994.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not know the original location.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not know the original location.

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Since the provenance of the manuscript is unknown, it is impossible to answer questions regarding the production of the text.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: This manuscript is part of a collection of around 1200 bamboo slips acquired by the Shanghai Museum in 1994 from the Hong Kong Antiquities Market. Scholarship is inclined to think that these manuscripts were buried together in the same tomb, but, unfortunately, being looted, it cannot be known for sure.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– Field doesn't know

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: This manuscript fits a larger discussion on the existence of ghosts and spirits (e.g., Mohists, Ruists) and their efficacy in rewarding the good and punishing the wicked.

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts and spirits were believed to punish the wicked and reward the good. This capacity of ghosts and spirits is recognized in the Guishen zhi ming 鬼神之神明, yet it is not always efficacious.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The text is part of a larger discussion on the existence and the role of ghosts and spirits.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: none.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: The manuscript lacks an explicit reference to spirit-body distinction.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: There is no explicit characterization of the afterlife in this manuscript, yet the existence of *gui* 鬼 (ghosts) implies that the author believed that humans become ghosts after death. That ghosts are born from humans after death is stated plainly in another manuscript from the Shanghai Museum collection, the *Fan wu liu xing* 凡物流形: 鬼生於人.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– No

Notes: There is no explicit reference to a supreme high-god, but it cannot be ruled out that it might have been included among the Gui shen 鬼神.

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– Field doesn't know

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– Yes

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Specify: According to this manuscript, ghosts, as well as spirits, have knowledge of this world and of human actions, and based on this knowledge they either reward or punish people. This knowledge, with both divine and moral connotations, is defined as ming 明. Yet, in contrast with Mohist theories advocated in the Mozi 墨子, chapter Ming gui 明鬼, this manuscript claims that there are areas in which gui and shen are not perspicuous. The text though does not specify in which domains gui and shen possess the ming and in which domains they do not. The text also poses the doubt as to whether they have the power to always be perspicuous and choose to not use it, or whether they actually lack that power on some occasions.
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– Field doesn't know

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: According to this manuscript, both spirits and ghosts have knowledge of this world and of human actions, and based on this knowledge they either reward or punish people. This knowledge, with both divine and moral connotations, is defined as ming 明. Yet, in contrast

with Mohist theories advocated in the Mozi 墨子, chapter Ming gui 明鬼, this manuscript claims that there are areas in which gui and shen are not perspicuous. The text though does not specify in which domains gui and shen possess the ming and in which domains they do not. The text also poses the doubt as to whether they have the power to always be perspicuous and choose to not use it, or whether they actually lack that power on some occasions.

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: The manuscript only focuses on the ming 明 (brilliant insight, perspicuity) of ghosts and spirits.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: None.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Field doesn't know

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Only the general categories of gui 鬼 and shen 神 are presented in the text.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

- Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: The text does not specify what ghosts and spirits care about. From the text, it is understood that ghosts and spirits can observe humans to reward the good and punish the wicked, but the text does not explicitly state what is considered good and what is considered wicked. According to the manuscript, sometimes good people are punished, while some wicked people are rewarded, because the insight of ghosts and spirits is not completely reliable.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Political failure?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Defeat in battle?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Sickness or illness?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other?

–Specify: The text does not specify the ways in which ghosts and spirits can punish humans, yet from the examples cited (e.g., Jie and Zhou) some wicked people face death as a punishment.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Consists of good luck?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– Yes

Notes: Yao, Shun, Yu, and Tang examples in the text are brought out to show how good rulers are rewarded with honor and success.

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other?

– Specify: Rewards, according to the examples given in the manuscript, include long life, political success and stability, honor, and prosperity in the tianxia 天下.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A state

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Due to the unknown provenance of the text, we have no information regarding the control over the reproduction of the text.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Due to the unknown provenance of the text, we have no information regarding the control over the destruction of the text.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Education in China has been primarily restricted to males for centuries.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Guishen zhi ming 鬼神之明, Brindley, Erica. "“the Perspicuity of Ghosts and Spirits” and the Problem of Intellectual Affiliations in Early China”. *Journal of the American Oriental Society* 129, no. 2 (2009): 215–36.

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